

Katia Dolle Method® in ASD: Single Case Study — Case 001 [MKD-ASD-001], Phase 1 (21 months); A-B follow-up; Mexico, 2023–2024.

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KEYWORDS: Autism Spectrum Disorder, complementary therapies, naturopathy, single case study.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by difficulties in communication, social interaction, and repetitive behavior patterns. Research is needed on new therapeutic approaches that take into account its potential multicausal origin and multisystem involvement. The theory of complex systems applied to health suggests that for an intervention to be effective, it must be multidimensional.

Case presentation: In December 2022, a 4-year-old girl was evaluated for symptoms consistent with ASD and sensory, communicative, and socioemotional alterations. The diagnosis of moderate-severe autism was confirmed through standardized interviews, and a low developmental profile was documented in several neurodevelopmental domains.

Intervention: The Katia Dolle Method® programs for ASD (a complex naturopathic intervention) were implemented from March 2023 to November 2024 in a personalized manner. These included: 1. Nutrition; 2. Naturopathic supplementation; 3. Parent school and parental coaching; 4. Structured neurostimulation; 5. Monitoring and follow-up.

Results: The progress reported by the parents through continuous observation was corroborated by temporal comparisons of scores on three standardized instruments: ATEC (autism severity improved from severe to mild), DP-3 (general developmental index improved from very low to average), and SENA (all problem indicators decreased while capacity indicators increased).

Conclusions: Through a complex naturopathic intervention (Katia Dolle Method®) combined with parental coaching applied over 21 months, a 4-year-old girl significantly improved the severity of her ASD and the symptomatology associated with the disorder (ATEC –85.7%), exceeding the outcomes expected with other types of therapies documented in the scientific literature. The general DP-3 index rose from 62 to 91 in the last 12 months of intervention,

representing a 29-point gain (~2.4 SD). This increase (+46.8%) goes beyond what is expected from maturation, and the “catch-up effect” reflects an accelerated developmental trajectory that substantially reduced the gap with her neurotypical peers. Convergent improvements in socioemotional domains (SENA) support the clinical robustness of the observed change.

INTRODUCTION

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by impairments in social interaction and communication, associated with restricted interests and stereotyped behaviors. It has a neurobiological basis and is associated, among other findings, with complex changes in synaptogenesis and neuronal connectivity. It shows high heritability and heterogeneous etiology, which includes genetic, immunological, and environmental causes [1] [2] [3]. Although ABA is one of the therapies with the strongest evidence to date for ASD, international protocols also acknowledge combined or multimodal approaches that include biological, nutritional, sensory, or developmental interventions, although the quality of evidence for the latter remains heterogeneous. Further research is needed on new therapeutic approaches that consider the possible multicausal origin and multisystem involvement of the disorder [4] [5] [6].

Psychoneuroimmunoendocrinology (PNIE) is a scientific paradigm that integrates the psyche with the nervous, immune, and endocrine systems. It posits that disorders are not caused by a single imbalance but rather by the interaction of multiple biological and environmental factors. From this perspective, the various systems (nervous, immune, endocrine, digestive, psychological, etc.) interact dynamically. Complexity theory in health suggests that adaptive systems require attention to patterns and feedback loops rather than simple cause-effect relationships. ASD is a disorder of multicausal origin and multisystem involvement, and therefore an effective intervention must likewise be multidimensional. The World Naturopathic Federation (WNF) [7] emphasizes that patient-centered multimodal approaches are paramount in naturopathic care. A complex naturopathic intervention system seeks to influence several aspects of the organism simultaneously, understanding that improvements arise from the interaction and synergy of multiple factors.

In this context, the Katia Dolle Method® programs for ASD propose a complex naturopathic intervention based on PNIE, which addresses in a coordinated way the biological imbalances interconnected with behavioral problems. To adequately address neurodevelopmental disorders with multisystem biological alterations, this method was developed through an extensive process of case research and analysis, integrating naturopathic knowledge with empirically validated therapeutic tools. It consists of a set of therapeutic actions targeting several biological domains to reduce both the physical and psychological difficulties of children with ASD, through a structured and personalized approach, promoting significant improvements in their health, quality of life, and all areas of neurodevelopment [8].

CASE PRESENTATION

After an uncomplicated pregnancy and a scheduled cesarean delivery, the girl showed normal development until 18 months of age, including bonding, eye contact, laughter, seeking attention, babbling, and some words such as “dad.” By the age of 18 months, she no longer laughed, did not respond to her name, stopped babbling, and no longer even said “dad.” Between ages 2 and 3, the family consulted a neuropsychologist who indicated that the child had global developmental delay, with skills corresponding to 17 months at a chronological age of 36 months. Occupational and speech therapy, swimming, and a program based on the Denver methodology were initiated.

At 4 years of age, she underwent an evaluation with several tests (ADI-R, ADOS-2, BATELLE, GARS-2, SCQ, PS2, among others) and received a diagnosis of moderate-severe autism. EEG recordings revealed abnormal graphoelements in the left hemisphere and a disorganized, immature rhythm. Treatment with psychopharmaceuticals was prescribed, along with what the mother described as a “very general and flexible” diet. After two months, the parents discontinued both the psychopharmaceuticals and the diet, as no positive changes were observed, and they enrolled in the Katia Dolle Method® program for ASD, simultaneously discontinuing the therapies that had been in place.

Diagnostic evaluation

Table 1 details the main conclusions of the assessment tests (ADI-R, ADOS-2, BATELLE, GARS-2, SCQ, PS2, among others) conducted in December 2022, three months before the intervention began. Difficulties were observed across all neurodevelopmental domains, with features consistent with ASD and a developmental profile well below the child’s chronological age.

Table 1: Diagnostic evaluation

Test	Category	Description
ADOS-2	Diagnosis	Moderate–severe autism according to ADOS-2 mapping (7 out of 10 points).
BATELLE	Developmental age	Developmental age of 23 months compared with chronological age of 48 months.
GARS-2S	ASD behavior scale	78% probability of behaviors attributable to autism.
PS-2	Sensory profile	SPECTATOR quadrant: greater need for auditory, tactile, and vestibular stimuli.
ADI-R	Diagnostic interview	Abnormal development with behavioral, social, and communication features consistent with an autism condition.

Test	Category	Description
Language area assessment	Preverbal skills	Pre-language skills corresponding to 4 months of age compared with chronological age of 48 months, indicating difficulties in all language components (semantic, morphosyntactic, phonological, and pragmatic).
Qualitative observations	Behavior observed during assessment	Greater interest in objects than in people; poor eye contact; no spontaneous response to name; lack of reciprocity in various activities; absence of word production; difficulty generating and understanding communicative gestures; presence of vocal stereotypies; absence of new, spontaneous symbolic play; difficulty with shared enjoyment; absence of reciprocal social smile; few facial expressions; inadequate social initiations; disruptive behaviors during activity transitions; hand-flapping and unusual sensory-seeking behaviors.
Overall clinical impression	General summary	<p>Persistent deficits in social reciprocity, communicative intent, verbal communication, spontaneous use of gestures to communicate cognitive states, quality of social initiation and response, and initiation and response to joint attention.</p> <p>Difficulties in the use of descriptive, conventional, instrumental, and/or emotional gestures; generation of spontaneous symbolic play; functional interaction with peers.</p> <p>Presence of stereotyped movements and unusual sensory-driven behaviors.</p>

Clinical findings

At the start of the intervention, in March 2023, the parents described the symptoms and signs associated with ASD observed in their daughter. In addition, the main findings from blood, urine, and stool analyses revealed several biological alterations. Table 2 summarizes these initial ASD-related symptoms and signs, together with altered biological variables.

Table 2: Initial clinical findings

Category	Description
Qualitative clinical data (observed by parents before the intervention)	Stress upon contact, intolerance to noise, panic in new places, irrational fears, tantrums, aggression, self-injury, absence of speech, lack of comprehension, social isolation, no functional play, insensitivity to pain, inability to perceive danger, elopement, inability to touch paint or playdough, extreme food selectivity, no sphincter control.
Quantitative clinical data (initial laboratory results)	<p>Urine: Metals: (As, Cd, Cs, Pb, Hg, Cu) ↑; Minerals: (Ca, Se, Fe, Mg, P, Cr, B, Zn) ↓.</p> <p>Stool (microbiology): imbalanced commensal flora; dysbiotic flora (<i>Citrobacter</i>, <i>Enterobacter</i>, <i>Klebsiella</i>); yeasts +.</p> <p>Blood (organs/systems): ALT 52 U/L ↑, creatinine 0.46 mg/dL ↓, dopamine 116 pg/mL ↑, cortisol 13.3 µg/dL.</p> <p>Blood (type III allergies): elevated reaction to 10 foods (oats, barley, spelt, gluten, wheat, rye, lemon, romaine lettuce, egg, almond).</p>

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

The intervention was based on a personalized complex naturopathic approach developed through the Katia Dolle Method[®], with the following main axes of action:

1. Nutrition:

Substitution of foods to reduce cytokines according to type III food allergy results, improve intestinal permeability, and correct intestinal dysbiosis by promoting protective flora and reducing dysbiosis. Parental coaching was provided to design balanced menus and highly nutritious diets.

2. Naturopathic supplementation:

Supplement subscription guidelines were organized in two-month blocks, with semiannual review and adjustment based on laboratory tests and clinical history. A wide range of supplements was used (37 different ones throughout the intervention), aimed at modulating immune, neurological, neuroendocrine, and digestive (absorption) functions, as well as detoxification of toxins and metals. Primary imbalances were addressed first, followed by secondary and tertiary levels in a structured order (*).

3. Parent school and parental coaching:

Initially, parents received intensive training in nutrition, natural remedies, and healthy lifestyle habits, among others. Later, training focused on neurodevelopmental stimulation and behavioral management, through parental coaching with psychoeducational guidance.

4. Structured neurostimulation:

Progressive, tailored guidelines were established according to the child's progress, with specific objectives in behavior, language, motor skills, and socioemotional abilities.

5. Monitoring and follow-up:

Periodic evaluations included blood, urine, and stool analyses, as well as the application of standardized scales (ATEC, DP-3, SENA). Individualized adjustments were made in each therapeutic block according to clinical and biological evolution.

(* The sequence in which various biological alterations and neurodevelopmental deficits are addressed is determined by the Katia Dolle Method[®] according to each specific case. Improving certain organic variables first, before addressing others, ensures that key aspects

are strengthened prior to moving on, and a rotational focus across these axes requires precise understanding of the interrelation between both biological and behavioral variables that condition the disorder.)

RESULTS AND FOLLOW-UP

Below we present the intervention follow-up timeline along with a summary of the main outcomes.

Table 3. Timeline of intervention, follow-up, and main results

Date	Intervention / Follow-up	Main results (summary)
March 2023 (baseline)	Enrollment in the program. Online parent school (nutrition, menus, food rotation, natural remedies). Initial evaluation with laboratory tests (blood, urine, stool) and clinical history. Supplementation subscription for 6 months. Start of dietary re-education.	ATEC 112 (severe autism). Multiple laboratory abnormalities.
Oct / Nov 2023	Second anamnesis questionnaire. Nutrition monitoring. Repeat laboratory tests (blood and urine). Updated supplementation plan. Application of DP-3 and SENA. Start of specific neurostimulation and behavioral guidelines.	ATEC 38 (moderate–mild autism). DP-3 general development index: 62 (very low range). Initial clinical improvements observed. No regressions or side effects.
May 2024	Repeat stool microbiology analysis. New supplementation block (6 months). Application of DP-3. Start of specific training in stimulation and behavior (parental coaching). Ongoing general and personalized stimulation/behavior coaching.	DP-3 general development index: 83 (low range). Improvements in intestinal flora, nutrition, and toxin excretion. No regressions or side effects.
Oct / Nov 2024	Third anamnesis questionnaire. Repeat laboratory tests (blood and urine). Adjustments to supplementation. Application of DP-3 and SENA. Review of stimulation program.	ATEC 16 (mild autism). DP-3: 91 (average range). SENA shows global socioemotional improvements. School performance normalized. No regressions or side effects.

Timeline of quantitative and qualitative data

The quantitative timeline shows the evolution of main laboratory and standardized test results.

Table 4. Timeline of quantitative data

Date	Test or analysis	Result	Evolution / Comment
March 2023 (baseline)	ATEC	112	Severe autism (>104).
	Laboratory tests	As, Cd, Cs, Pb, Hg ↑; dysbiotic flora +; fungi +; hepatocellular stress; food intolerances; mineral malabsorption; neuroendocrine dysregulation.	Significant initial intoxication, profound dysbiosis, altered neuroendocrine axis, nutrient deficiencies.
	EEG	Abnormal graphoelements, immature rhythm.	Baseline neurophysiological alteration.
April 2023	ATEC	77	Severity reduced to moderate–severe (104–75).
Nov 2023	DP3	62	General development index in very low range (<70).
	ATEC	38	Severity reduced to mild–moderate (30–54).

Date	Test or analysis	Result	Evolution / Comment
	Raven	122	High non-verbal intelligence (120–130), intellectual disability ruled out.
	SENA	Developmental delay 77. Rigidity 70. Emotional regulation problems 61. Personal resources 21. Social integration and competence 26. Emotional intelligence 22.	Difficulties in developmental delay, rigidity, and emotional regulation. Low resources in social integration and emotional intelligence. Critical items: occasional self-injury and frequent loss of control.
May 2024	EEG	Irritative frontotemporal alteration.	Neurological immaturity
	DP3	83	Clear improvement, approaching average range (85–115).
	Laboratory tests	Fungi –; Reduction of commensal flora to <i>Leuconostoc lactis</i> + <i>Streptococcus salivarius</i> .	Correction of profound dysbiosis due to bacteria and fungi.
Oct 2024	Laboratory tests	Cd, Cs, Pb, Ni +; Anti-Epstein Barr nuclear antigen IgG 421.0 U/mL ↑; ALT 100 U/L ↑; AST 37 U/L ↑; Dopamine <45 pg/mL; Cortisol 11.6 µg/dL ↓.	Partial toxin elimination, hepatic dysfunction due to recent mononucleosis, neurotransmitter regulation. Malnutrition corrected.
Nov 2024 (final)	ATEC	16	Mild autism (0–30).
	DP3	91	General development within average range (85–115)
	SENA	Developmental delay 67. Rigidity 41. Emotional regulation problems 37. Personal resources 48. Social integration and competence 54. Emotional intelligence 43.	Global profile normalized: reduced developmental delay and unusual behaviors, disappearance of critical items, consolidation of age-appropriate personal resources.

The qualitative timeline shows parents’ month-to-month descriptions of the child’s progressive achievements.

Table 5. Timeline of qualitative data

Date	Evolution of symptoms and signs reported by parents
Mar 2023	Pinches and scratches when hearing someone cry; pinches mother and sisters when stressed; undigested food in stools; no sense of danger; nonverbal; covers ears and throws objects when stressed; rarely smiles; insensitive to others’ feelings; does not respond to name (appears deaf); inappropriate play; insensitivity to pain; lack of bond with mother; irrational fears; severe sensory problems; mental rigidity with clothing; avoids touch; elopement; screen obsession.
Apr 2023	Achieves day and night continence by being taken to urinate once at night; accepts familiar children and company; participates in birthday parties (social improvement); improved food selectivity; starts functional play; begins to understand basic instructions; begins to imitate; loses irrational fears.
May 2023	Greater mental flexibility with clothing; begins to tolerate textures; allows touch and hair brushing (sensory improvement); no longer elopes; follows schoolwork instructions.
Jun 2023	Complete sphincter control.
Jul 2023	Completely abandons food selectivity. Increased autonomy (dressing, eating, hygiene). Recognizes colors, objects, environment.
Aug 2023	Takes supplements independently, without coercion. Points to body parts. Responds to her name. Laughs and smiles.
Sep 2023	Identifies family members. Initiates social play spontaneously. No longer pinches. Imitates sounds.
Oct 2024	Begins to concentrate and imitate better. Improved fine motor skills. Interest in stories. Retains rational fears. Begins to explore creative materials.
Nov 2023	Increased mental flexibility and reduced rigidity. Perceives distances and dangers.
Dec 2023	Begins humming (songs) and using words (verbs, nouns) with communicative intent.
Jan 2024	Recognizes letters, says syllables, begins global reading. Improved school performance.

Date	Evolution of symptoms and signs reported by parents
Feb 2024	Increased vocabulary used appropriately. Functional comprehension and use of verbalizations of actions.
Mar 2024	Begins to request desired items. Greater spontaneity. Overcomes screen obsession.
Apr 2024	Greater sensory flexibility. Accepts new experiences (e.g., playing in mud). Excited about dressing up for the first time.
May 2024	Improved understanding of various social situations and related socioemotional language.
Jun 2024	Uses 5-word sentences. Applies learned language to future situations. Answers questions instead of repeating.
Jul 2024	Handles stressful situations. Calm and cooperative at dental visit.
Aug 2024	Completes a 100-piece puzzle (age-appropriate). Initiates social table games. Spontaneously engages in activities
Sep 2024	Begins literacy: matching image–word. Spontaneous comprehension and use of verbs and concepts.
Oct 2024	Role play. Creative play. High adaptability to new and stressful environments.
Nov 2024	Symbolic play. Improvements in cognition, language, sociability, and motor skills. Performs choreographies. Has 2 friends. Verbally requests help with three-word phrases. Learns and imitates immediately. Answers questions she understands. Age-appropriate fine motor skills. Age-appropriate autonomy. Spontaneous language. Begins to joke. Works independently at school at the same level as peers.

Comparative results of ATEC, DP-3, and SENA

The following section presents the temporal changes in scores on three standardized tests. Significant improvements were observed across all neurodevelopmental domains, with a marked reduction in severity.

Graph 1. Temporal comparison of total ATEC score.

The first ATEC measurement (112) placed the child in the severe autism range. One month after starting the intervention, the score decreased to the lower limit of the severe–moderate range (77). At 8 months, it improved to the moderate–mild level (38). After 21 months, the score reached the mild autism level (16). Over 21 months, the ATEC score decreased by 96 points.

Graph 2. Temporal comparison of ATEC subscales.

Reductions across all ATEC subscales indicate significant improvements in problems associated with the four neurodevelopmental areas assessed by this questionnaire: 1. Language and communication; 2. Sociability; 3. Sensory and cognitive awareness; 4. Health / physical behavior.

Graph 3. Temporal comparison of DP-3 scores.

The Developmental Profile 3 (DP-3) provides age-adjusted standardized scores (M = 100, SD = 15). Thus, changes in scores reflect relative variations compared to the normative population of the same age, not merely

the passage of time [9]. Over 12 months, the child progressed from the clinically significant delay range (<70) to the average range (85–115), with a total increase of +29 points (~2.4 SD). In normative terms, this change cannot be attributed to the mere passage of time and is consistent with an accelerated, clinically relevant developmental trajectory (see annex).

It should be noted that no DP-3 was administered at the beginning of the intervention. Therefore, the evolution during the first 9 months, when ATEC improved from 112 (severe) to 38 (moderate-mild), was not captured by this test. Consequently, if DP-3 had been measured at baseline, the magnitude of change would have been greater than what was documented.

Graph 4. Temporal comparison of SENA scores.

The SENA results show that all problem indicators decreased, while all capacity indicators increased. The only three indicators that crossed over in the comparison lines were the three positive indicators measured (personal resources; social integration and competence; emotional intelligence).

As with the DP-3, the first SENA measurement was taken after 9 months of intervention. Thus, the improvements achieved when autism severity decreased from severe to moderate–mild (according to ATEC) were not documented by this instrument.

Table 6. Comparative summary of initial, intermediate, and final ATEC, DP-3, and SENA results

Test	Initial value	Intermediate value	Final value	Absolute Δ	% Change
ATEC (total)	112	38	16	-96	-85,7 %
DP-3 (General Development Index)		62	91	+29	+46,8 %
SENA – Personal resources		21	28	+7	+33,3 %
SENA – Developmental delay		77	67	-10	-13,0 %
SENA – Social integration and competence		26	54	+28	+107,7 %
SENA – Emotional intelligence		22	43	+21	+95,5 %

This table summarizes the comparative results of the main standardized tests between the beginning and end of the intervention, highlighting the magnitude and direction of the observed changes. The results show consistent and clinically relevant improvements in multiple dimensions (behavioral, adaptive, and socioemotional), supporting the robustness and coherence of the documented change.

DISCUSSION

The evidence regarding complementary therapies in ASD remains under debate, and clinical guidelines emphasize the need for professional supervision to ensure safety [10]. To date, there are insufficient studies supporting the efficacy of a multimodal naturopathic approach in ASD; however, the scientific literature highlights the importance of addressing both multifactorial etiology and pathogenesis in practice, as well as the relevance of investigating new therapeutic approaches [1]. Thus, there is a need to test, through research, the effectiveness of a systematic, adaptable, and reproducible methodology capable of addressing the complexity of a disorder with multifactorial origin and multisystem involvement such as ASD.

Unlike conventional ASD therapies that focus on behavioral modification, the complex naturopathic intervention of the Katia Dolle Method® addresses both the regulation of biological systems, implementing strategies of immunonutrition and supplementation aimed at neuroregeneration and the modulation of altered biochemical processes in ASD, and the training of parents through an online school covering child health, nutrition, reduction of adverse environmental factors, behavior, and neurostimulation.

This study aligns with previous research documenting improvements following complementary strategies in children with ASD. Studies on specific diets have shown that eliminating gluten and casein in children with ASD can generate significant improvements in several domains [4]. Other research has also reported associations between gastrointestinal dysfunctions and ASD symptoms [11]. Studies on supplementation therapies have documented positive changes in cognition and behavior in children with ASD following the administration of certain micronutrients [12]. However, the ordered integration and adaptive personalization of these and many other principles within a complex multimodal

naturopathic methodology is what justifies the unusual effectiveness observed in reducing the severity of the disorder in this single-case study.

A common limitation of case reports is the inability to establish causality. However, the fact that no other specific ASD therapies were undertaken (only generic equine therapy and Montessori support teacher) during the intervention period, combined with the magnitude and coherence of the observed improvements, supports the hypothesis that the studied intervention contributed significantly to the clinical evolution. The standardized assessments used to evaluate the case's progression were completed by the parents, which implies a potential bias of observation and expectation. The parents were informed of this in order to promote objectivity.

CONCLUSIONS

Through a complex naturopathic intervention (Katia Dolle Method®) combined with parental coaching (carried out with great rigor by the parents [13]) applied over 21 months, a 4-year-old girl significantly improved the severity of her ASD and the symptomatology associated with the disorder (ATEC -85.7%), surpassing the outcomes expected with other therapies documented in the scientific literature. The DP-3 general index rose from 62 to 91 in the last 12 months of intervention, representing a gain of 29 points (~2.4 SD). This increase (+46.8%) exceeds what would be expected from maturation alone, and the observed "catch-up effect" reflects an accelerated developmental trajectory that substantially shortened the gap with her neurotypical peers. Convergent improvements in socioemotional domains (SENA) support the clinical robustness of the observed change.

The outcome observed in this single-case study falls within the ranges documented when applying the Katia Dolle Method® in a broader sample, as demonstrated in a retrospective study conducted with 183 participants [7]. This example constitutes a reference model for approaching autism from a complexity framework, suggesting the need to evaluate results across multiple dimensions (behavioral scales, language tests, biomarkers, neurodevelopment, nutrition, etc.) to capture the broad impact of a complex intervention. It also highlights the importance of formulating multimodal causal hypotheses that must therefore be addressed jointly.

Prospective and controlled studies are needed to validate these observations. Even so, case studies provide valuable preliminary evidence, generate hypotheses, and demonstrate the clinical applicability of complexity theory as a basis for future research.

Patient perspective

The parents expressed gratitude not only for addressing their daughter's biological problems, but also for being taught how to maintain improvements for life:

"Showing me the step-by-step path and making me realize that much depends on how much I work (stimulate) with my daughter now that the biological aspect is being addressed is something wonderful. Before, I had the desire to help her but I did not know how, nor what should come first or after. The

biological barriers prevented connection, and my daughter did not recognize me, which made my day-to-day life extremely difficult and frustrating.”

Informed consent

The authors certify that they obtained all the necessary consent forms from the parents of the child involved. In these forms, the parents gave their consent for images and other clinical information to be published.

The parents understand that their names and initials will not be published and that every effort will be made to conceal their identity, although complete anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Funding

This study received no external funding. The intervention was provided at no cost to the family, since, according to the agreement signed, full reimbursement of the program fees was granted upon completion of the adherence required for the research. The costs associated with the development of the study (professional time, follow-up, and analyses) were assumed without remuneration by the Katia Dolle Foundation.

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ANNEX

DP-3 Evolution: Baseline vs. final in relation to the normative mean

It can be observed that the child progressed from an initial score within the severe delay range (62, < -2 SD) to a final score close to the mean (91, within the expected range), recovering nearly 2.4 standard deviations in 12 months.